

DISTINGUISHING FEATURES OF CONTRASTIVE AND COMPARATIVE LINGUISTICS

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Navbahor tuman 2-son texnikumi xalqaro ta'lim dasturlarini muvofiqlashtirish bo'limi boshliq

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada kontrastiv lingvistika, qiyosiy tilshunoslik va konfrontativ lingvistika terminlarining mazmun-mohiyati hamda ularning o'zaro farqli jihatlari yoritilgan. qiyosiy va kontrastiv tadqiqotlarning maqsad va vazifalarini tahlil qilib, tillarni qiyoslash jarayonida o'xshash va farqli jihatlarni aniqlash muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, maqolada kontrastiv lingvistikaning nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati, ayniqsa chet tillarini o'qitish hamda tarjima jarayonidagi o'rni ko'rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kontrastiv lingvistika, qiyosiy tilshunoslik, konfrontativ lingvistika, til tizimi, qiyoslash, til farqlari, til o'xshashliklari, lingvodidaktika, tarjimashunoslik, tilshunoslik.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются сущность и особенности терминов «контрастивная лингвистика», «сопоставительное языкознание» и «конфронтативная лингвистика», а также их отличительные черты. Автор анализирует цели и задачи сопоставительных и контрастивных исследований, подчеркивая важность выявления сходств и различий между языками. Кроме того, в статье раскрывается теоретическое и практическое значение контрастивной лингвистики, особенно в области преподавания иностранных языков и переводоведения.

Ключевые слова: Контрастивная лингвистика, сопоставительное языкознание, фронтативная лингвистика, языковая система, сопоставление, языковые различия, языковые сходства, лингводидактика, переводоведение, языкознание.

Annotation. This article discusses the essence and distinguishing features of the terms “contrastive linguistics,” “comparative linguistics,” and “confrontative linguistics.” The author analyzes the aims and objectives of comparative and contrastive studies, emphasizing the importance of identifying similarities and differences between languages. The article also highlights the theoretical and practical significance of contrastive linguistics, particularly in foreign language teaching and translation studies.

Keywords: Contrastive linguistics, comparative linguistics, confrontative linguistics, language system, comparison, language differences, language similarities, linguodidactics, translation studies, linguistics.

Today, alongside the term “contrastive linguistics,” which is the most actively used term in terminology, the terms “comparative linguistics” or “confrontative linguistics” are also used as alternative variants for this concept. This situation has emerged because scientific views within the field are still in the developmental stage, and opinions have not yet been fully formed.

According to M.T. Irisqulov, “comparative linguistics synchronically compares two languages regardless of their degree of relatedness or geographical location.” Furthermore, comparative linguistics aims to identify the similarities and differences between languages belonging to different systems. Usually, the internal characteristics of the compared languages are first studied separately, after which the research findings are compared.

A. Gudavichyus defines comparative linguistics as follows: “Two or more languages are studied through the method of comparison. In such an approach, both similarities and differences are important for the researcher.” In his book *Comparative Semasiology of the Lithuanian and Russian Languages*, A. Gudavichyus defines the discipline as “a field that studies the lexical systems of two or more languages through the method of comparison.” While attempting to distinguish between the terms contrastive and comparative linguistics, the author emphasizes that contrastive analysis is limited to two languages. He explains that contrastive analysis mainly serves practical, especially linguo didactic, purposes. “Studying one language through the ‘mirror’ of another language is a manifestation of contrastive research.” Thus, contrastive studies examine the distinctive and opposing features of a language in comparison with another selected language, usually the native language. This idea is also supported by R.A. Budagov: “When studying word combinations from a comparative perspective, not only similarities but also differences are important and interesting.” Such a view emphasizes the distinction between contrastive syntax and comparative linguistics.

The use of the term comparative linguistics has a long tradition and dates back to the earliest attempts to theoretically understand the comparative study of languages. In later stages, however, it began to be used less frequently because the meaning expressed by the term was not uniform and remained somewhat vague. This also indicates that scientific consistency within the field had not yet been sufficiently established.

Linguist I.F. Isenova, discussing the goals, tasks, methods, and general principles of comparative linguistics and contrastive linguistics, emphasizes the following: “Unlike comparative linguistics, the subject of contrastive linguistics is the comparison of languages in a linguodidactic direction, determined by such comparison of languages that helps identify and describe aspects facilitating the learning of a second (foreign) language, as well as explaining discrepancies in grammatical and semantic systems of different languages.” Thus, opposition and contrast are implied.

V.M. Mokienko considered it extremely important to distinguish comparative linguistics from contrastive linguistics. He noted that “the first term is directed toward identifying the distinctive features of the compared languages, while the second expresses the process of comparing both differences and common features between languages.” In our view, however, these explanations have been interchanged. In fact, contrastive linguistics aims to identify the distinctive features of compared languages, whereas comparative linguistics expresses the process of comparing both differences and commonalities between languages.

When speaking about the distinction between comparative linguistics and contrastive linguistics, Zh.M. Omasheva believes that studying language units from the perspective of comparing their structural-systemic and functional characteristics remains one of the most urgent tasks of modern linguistics. It is well known that language systems are characterized by complexity and dynamism. Therefore, theoretical and practical forms of comparative research require language processes to be viewed as systemic structures.

Thus, the distinction between these directions should be made from the standpoint of the object and subject of research. The differences between comparative and contrastive studies are determined by the goals and tasks established by the researcher: comparative linguistics is studied based on theoretical and practical aims, whereas contrastive linguistics compares two language systems to identify features specific to each language system and to improve second-language teaching. However, it should also be emphasized that contrastive linguistics is connected not only

with practical tasks related to second-language teaching but also with drawing theoretical conclusions by identifying the unique characteristics of each language through contrastive comparison.

Contrastive linguistics emerged as a separate field from comparative linguistics, and today contrastive studies are investigated within the framework of linguistic sciences. According to V.N. Yartseva, it exists as an independent theoretical direction with its own distinct object of study.

To demonstrate the differences between comparative and contrastive linguistics more clearly, I.A. Sternin uses the following diagrams.

In comparative linguistics, each language is studied as a separate system, and the obtained results are then compared within corresponding levels. In contrastive linguistics, however, the analysis focuses on how a language phenomenon in the first language is expressed through linguistic means in the second language. Here, the meaning of a linguistic unit in the first language may be expressed through several different linguistic units belonging to different levels in the second language, and vice versa.

For example, the semantic field of the English word *weekend* in Uzbek includes the time from Friday afternoon until Sunday evening. Similarly, the Uzbek word *o'rmon* corresponds to two English words: *wood* and *forest*. In turn, the word *wood* also means timber or firewood in addition to forest.

Another term used synonymously with contrastive linguistics is confrontative linguistics. The term “confrontative linguistics” was introduced into science by L. Zabrocki simultaneously with the term “contrastive linguistics” and became widely used in Eastern European countries. Although linguists attempted to distinguish the semantic scope of these two terms, scholars such as Yartseva, Mirkin, Yusupov, and Kashkin still use them as synonymous terms.

Many scholars have expressed their views on the relationship between contrastive and confrontative comparison of languages. One of them, V.Ya. Mirkin, concluded that contrastive comparison is significant within didactic comparative typology, whereas confrontative comparison is significant within theoretical typology. However, the various opinions expressed make it clear that contrastive or confrontative comparison of languages cannot be regarded as identical to typology. Especially, they cannot be viewed merely as forms of typology. Unlike typology, they require a specific list of compared languages. Pure typological description studies language and all its units and features as manifestations of human language in general. By contrast, contrastive description requires the selection of at least two object languages.

L.N. Grigoryeva proposes understanding confrontative linguistics as a theoretical direction and contrastive linguistics as a practical direction. There are also views that confrontative linguistics studies both similarities and differences between languages, whereas contrastive linguistics deals only with differences between languages. We also recognize contrastive and confrontative linguistics as terms denoting different fields. The object of study of confrontative linguistics is identical to that of comparative linguistics, since both investigate common and differing features of the languages under study. Contrastive linguistics, however, mainly examines points of opposition between languages.

G. Helbig explained that describing languages solely through a purely contrastive approach is insufficient for substantiating second-language teaching methodology. According to him, errors in second-language learning are caused not only by contrasts but often also by similarities between languages. Helbig called such an approach, which considers both differences and similarities between languages, “confrontative linguistics” and clearly defined the essence of the linguistic

analysis methodology underlying it. Thus, the meaning of confrontative linguistics used by Helbig corresponds to the concept of comparative linguistics in Russian linguistics. Therefore, Russian linguistics does not traditionally distinguish between confrontative and comparative linguistics.

According to V.G. Gak, contrastive linguistics is an established independent science with its own goals, object, and methods of analysis. “The general theoretical description of contrastive linguistics covers all language levels from phonology to stylistics and text theory. The increasing number of various studies devoted to the contrastive study of languages demonstrates the growing development and importance of contrastive linguistics in linguistics.” If contrastive linguistics is to be recognized as an independent science, then it becomes necessary to distinguish its terminological units theoretically.

According to I.A. Sternin, the purpose of contrastive linguistics is to identify differences between languages. “The object of study of contrastive linguistics is the comparison of the researcher’s native language with a second language.”

In most cases, only two languages are taken as the object of research in contrastive linguistics, usually the native language and a foreign language. One of the compared languages is taken as the basis, serving as the reference point for contrastive research. Its internal structure functions as a standard for comparing the distinctive features of the two languages. Usually, the native language serves as the basis, while the second language is the foreign language being studied.

According to A.V. Fyodorov, closely related languages, languages having some degree of genetic relationship, and even languages with no genetic connection at all can be contrasted with one another. For example, the opposing points between Uzbek and Uyghur, Uzbek and Chuvash, or Uzbek and English form the basis of contrastive studies.

In contrastive analysis, research is conducted not only in one direction but also in the opposite direction. According to I.A. Sternin, two foreign languages may also be studied in a contrastive manner, where one is taken as the basis and the other as the compared language. Even in such cases, the research is conducted in one direction: phenomena existing in the first language are studied in comparison with similar phenomena in the second language.

The primary task of contrastive linguistics is to identify the specific semantic and functional features of the language under study against the background of the compared language. By describing the semantic units of one language against the background of another, the national specificity of the units of the studied language becomes apparent.

Thus, the ideas discussed above indicate that contrastive and comparative (confrontative) linguistics are emerging as distinct branches in modern linguistics. This demonstrates the necessity of distinguishing them terminologically. We support recognizing contrastive linguistics as an independent discipline with its own specific features. It should be emphasized that, among multilingual disciplines, contrastive linguistics is distinguished primarily by its practical significance. This is the main feature that differentiates contrastive linguistics from other linguistic sciences concerned with the comparative study of languages.

As a result of applying the comparative method, which is a universal method of cognition, for various purposes, such linguistic fields as comparative-historical linguistics, typology, and comparative linguistics have emerged. Contrastive linguistics, which studies oppositions and contrasts between languages, developed on the basis of these fields.

The aim of contrastive linguistics is to identify oppositions and contrasts related to the specific features of at least two compared language systems and to investigate them by means of

the oppositional method. The genetic or areal relations of these languages, as well as their typological proximity or distance, cannot prevent them from becoming objects of comparative study. In this process, the main focus is placed on the contrasting and differing points between languages.

Contrastive linguistics has both purely theoretical and theoretical-practical directions. The theoretical direction serves the science of language theory. On the one hand, it identifies unique features and distinctions in the compared languages; on the other hand, through its theoretical issues, it contributes to the development of linguoculturology, translation studies, and the theory of linguistic universalities and unique features.

Contrastive analysis may be carried out on all levels of language units — from phonemes to supersyntactic wholes — as well as on the basis of their functional states and ethnocultural, sociolinguistic, and psycholinguistic foundations.

Under the conditions of globalization, the increasing need to study world languages, the development of translation theory, the growing attention in anthropocentric linguistics to the capacities of speakers and listeners, and the necessity to improve the quality and content of foreign language teaching are all important factors contributing to the development of contrastive linguistics.

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